

Technology in Education – Scope and Challenges

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Abstract

Technology refers to art, skill, science of craft, techniques, methods and processes applied in scientific investigation. Here Technology in education refers to the adoption of digital processes and tools to achieve goals in education field. It's a rapid move from the physical to digital - transformation. Transformation refers to the change in any form, nature or appearance. It indicates about the changes associated with digital technology application and integration into the aspects of human life and society. It also represents a massive cultural shift in the workplace which brings changes in every part of an organization. The education system has seen a lot of technological changes adopting new ways. We can find use of Digital whiteboards, mobile applications, tablet, smart phone, laptop etc. The students can enhance their knowledge at a deeper level. They can shape their future using the technology. It is easier, less expensive, flexible, i.e., they can collect information in laptop, mobile. It is also an opportunity to customize learning. Education sector using digital media helps to know about the new technology, new teaching methods, new learning methods, and new digital services. It brings the knowledge beyond the classroom. It is a great opportunity for all to access advanced information when they need it at the most. It helps to build learning modules in a faster way. With the help of digital transformation in education, we can find high-quality standard of education. Digital system makes students, educators more accountable and self-motivated.

Keywords: Effective Education, Culture, Reshaping, Unprecedented Information, Customize Learning.

Introduction

“Change is the Only Constant”

Technology in education refers to the changes adopted in education system using technology mainly to improve the skills and to have an effective education process.

Technology in education helps the educators and the students to get learning materials online, can enroll for online courses, so that they can have an enhanced communication network and can improve knowledge.

It is a simple platform which helps in rethinking, collaboration, innovation. It creates personalized and interactive learning experiences. It is to apply technology to teaching and learning in ways that reflect innovations in pedagogy.

Educators at present are required to adopt digital technologies, methodologies, mindset for the survival in this new digital world. Digital technology helps for the personalized learning, have changed from smart boards to AV-VR, Gamification, Application of the Internet of Things (IoT) and improved security.

Technology success in education: - Learning: Effective and rapid knowledge gaining through technology - Teaching: Teaching using technology - Leadership: creates culture, brings innovation, Assessment: Measuring - Infrastructure: Enabling access and effective use of infrastructure.

We can find - Expanded learning opportunities, High engagement learning, Competency-based learning, Assessment for learning, Collaborative learning, Sharing economy, Relevant and Regularly Updated Content, Next-gen learning for educators.

Review of Literature

Newman & Beetham, 2017, University of Bologna - A recent report from the UK digital education organisation Jisc, surveyed over 22,000 students from 74 UK and 10 international organisations, finding that “the full benefits of technology to support learning are yet to be realised, with technology more commonly used for convenience rather [than supporting] more effective pedagogy”.

George Westerman, 2016, Principal Research Scientist, MIT Sloan Initiative on the Digital Economy - “When digital transformation is done right, it’s like a caterpillar turning into a butterfly, but when done wrong, all you have is a really fast caterpillar.”

New York Times, 2014 Technology has a huge impact on the education sector. Six years ago ‘MOOCs’ (Massive Open Online Courses) became a buzzword with the New York Times going so far as to say 2012 was “the year of the MOOC.”

German Zawacki-Richter, Dolch & Müskens, 2017, Hamberg University - The study found a consistent and massive use of digital teaching and learning tool within German. Students (age group 14-29) are the biggest consumers and users of the internet and digital tools, 99.4% of German school students have a computer at home and spend 114 min on average weekdays using technology

Rebecca Frost Davis, St. Edward’s University Marden Paul, University of Toronto - Collaborating with faculty and academic leadership to apply technology to teaching and learning in ways that reflect innovations in pedagogy and the institutional mission.

International journal of media, technology and lifelong learning, 2017 Principal, Sweden - “When it comes to teaching overall, the tablets make it possible to easily make adjustments that fit every pupil’s needs, and especially those pupils with special needs”

Daniel Newman, 2015 CMO, Exploring all things Digital transformation - “Gone are the days where students are expected to sit quietly at their desks. Educational technology is succeeding in making learning collaborative and interactive. Augmented, virtual, and mixed reality are examples of transformative technology that enhance teacher instruction while simultaneously creating immersive lessons that are fun and engaging for the student. Virtual reality has the capability of bringing the outside world into the classroom and vice versa.”

Methodology

The paper uses secondary data for the purpose of analysis. It is collected through online articles, newspapers, magazines, books, journals and various websites.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the paper is to study:

- The impact of the technology in education

- The scope of technology in education
- The challenges of technology in education

Statement of the Problem

Any new invention in the society paving way for easy and comfortable life for the people at large has merits as well as demerits in it. Majority of educational institutions, students, educators are still cling to traditional method in India. They are unaware of these facilities and are not willing to change their way of teaching/learning methods using Digital technology. In this study we have made an attempt to study the effectiveness of technology in education system.

Scope, Pros And Cons of Technology in Education

- IOT – Internet of Thing, creates a more comfortable environment for students and teachers.
- Artificial Intelligence – clear explanation and step-by-step guide, it has increased accessibility - speech recognition and transcription for students who are deaf or hard of hearing
- Availability of Online Classes and Programs
- Virtual reality – students’ interaction, providing experience to the students
- Chatbots – provide answers and solutions for our questions
- It has enhanced professional thinking and practice to improve the quality of learning
- It meet the needs and priorities of the individual and the institution.
- Computer-based and online assessment processes
- Mobile devices accelerate knowledge and for gaining quick and easy access.
- Guidance and Instruction from Diverse Teachers, one student can be present in a multi-cultural online classroom with teachers with origins from South Africa, England, Brazil, Spain, Russia, and Poland all at the same time.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any student from any corner of the world can access to learning resources • Customized learning helps the student to get good results and to be more productive. • We also can get effective learning material which is available online. • Content: rich, deep, and up to date • Students can learn whenever they need • Promotes independent learning in students • Prepares students for the future • Students are Self- Motivated and More Accountable • Employability with Digital Learning Tools and Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster cheating in class and on assignments.It disconnect students from social interactions • Immense expenditures • Insufficient methods of teaching • Waste of valuable time • Major sources of distractions • Increase rate of cyber bullying • Major challenges for teachers • Extinct of good handwriting • Partial to the low-income group-

Analysis and Findings

1. Physical textbooks are slowly being replaced with technologies like, using mobile phone, laptops, iPads and various forms of devices connected to online media. With the development of online media, e-books, e-readers and learning programs, the textbook is now “extinct” in some areas. Digital transformation is more Convenient and time saving.
2. Information technology items (smartphone, laptop, tablets) that students owned are more. No students possessed no electronic devices of any kind.
3. Students seem to believe that technology is an important part of the academic process. They felt that technology was instrumental in successful teaching.
4. Without internet facility learners cannot gather any information in technology items, where all the students cannot afford the same.
5. Digital transformation in education has the positive impact on educational institutions, educators, students.

Recommendations

The educational institutions, educators and students need to be aware of the technological benefits as well as the threats caused by the innovations only then there shall be proper utilization of the developments. Protection against cyber threats, automated protection from malware and exploits. Protection from cyber-attacks has to be considered.

Conclusion

India which is a country of villages, where the literacy rate and internet awareness is very low, the concept of technology in education will not be so successful, but as per data collected who are using digital technology in education shows the clear evidence that the technology in education system have revealed better performance, it has increased in the overall performance of education institutions. It makes the work easier. Students have instant access to fresh information that can supplement their learning experience.

Bibliography

1. “Technology in Education: An Overview.” Education Week - Herold, Benjamin - Editorial Projects In Education, 07 June 2016.
2. “National Education Technology Plan – Office of Educational Technology.” - Office of Educational Technology.
3. “Lessons Learned for Effective Technology Implementation.” - Cited Research. Research Center – Center for Implementing Technology in Education.
4. <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/us/Documents/technology-media-telecommunications/us-tmt-digital-education-survey>.
5. <https://enginess.io/insights/3-digital-transformation-trends-education>
6. <https://www.dmcplc.co.uk/digital-transformation-trends-in-the-education-sector/>
7. <https://www.institutefordigitaltransformation.org/digital-strategy-in-education/>
8. <https://www.gettingsmart.com/2015/11/the-shift-to-digital-learning-10-benefits/>
9. <https://impactofinformationsystemsonociety.wordpress.com/2013/04/15/university-of-waterloo-class-survey-on-educational-technology/>